

BANKING STRATEGY AND ITS ROLE IN ENHANCING THE EFFECTIVENESS OF BANKING ACTIVITIES

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Abstract: The article discusses the fundamentals and trends of the development of the system of Islamic finance, the principles of Islamic financial institutions, as well as financial instruments that are used within the Islamic financial system. The distinctive features of Islamic and traditional banks are analyzed. Special attention is paid to the problems and prospects of the development of the Islamic finance system.

Keywords: bank strategy, asset, liability, management, marketing

Introduction

The main components of the modern banking market, as well as any other, are sellers, they are also commercial banks, and buyers are customers and partners. Banking competition is changing under the influence of changes in competition in other market sectors.

1. Production and services. In this sector, a commercial bank performs the role of a seller of banking services (account servicing, RKO), a financial intermediary (mortgage lending) and a buyer of resources necessary for the production process (machinery, everything for office equipment).

2. Consumption and services. Banking institutions perform the functions of financial intermediaries (consumer lending).

3. The labor market. In this sector, banks are buyers, they organize personnel work on the selection, evaluation, renewal, training and improvement of the qualification level of their employees.

4. Information products sector. In this market, commercial banks act as sellers of banking services through financial advice, and as buyers of resources necessary for the production process (software).

5. Real estate market. In this case, commercial banks act as financial intermediaries, buying land and real estate or selling collateral on non-repaid mortgages.

6. Financial services market. The role of a commercial bank is reduced to the foreign exchange market, the market of loans and securities. In these areas, the bank buys and sells temporary rights to use funds. Based on this, the development strategy of any bank should be considered as a management tool, as it sets strategic goals and is a goal-setting tool for the top management in the bank for active development in a competitive market. Based on the development strategy, the bank determines for itself what goals and in what perspective it intends to achieve. It can be said that the development strategy belongs to the category of the bank's governing documents. It should be noted that in addition to the strategy itself, the bank should develop such a document as "The procedure for developing and adopting the bank's development strategy". This document defines the entire process from preparation to approval of the bank's development strategy as the bank's guiding program document. Thus, this article addresses the issues of an instrumental approach to the bank's development strategy. The development strategy of the bank as a tool of banking strategic management

The main principles of the development of a commercial bank:

- ensuring a high level of stability, preserving the business reputation and image of the institution of socially important and significant;
- increase in the number of operations carried out by the bank, increase and improve the range of services provided, taking into account the ever-growing competition in the financial market;
- the growth of the bank's capital in accordance with the increase in active banking

operations; - maintaining the investment attractiveness of the bank, increasing profitability; - reduction of risks in banking, especially in credit activities, regulation of the quality of the bank loan portfolio; - ensuring an optimal level of liquidity and profitability of commercial bank operations; - increasing the customer base at the expense of individuals and enterprises of both medium and small businesses; - expansion of retail business: improving lending programs and attracting deposits that are used in the work; implementation of a program for providing a whole range of banking services for the population; updating plastic projects and increasing the number of ATMs; expanding the network of branches and the authority of the bank across the region, creating new office space; - creating a management system in a banking institution that meets modern business trends and complies with international standards, flexible interest and tariff policy; application of effective internal control and risk management; optimization and elimination of deficiencies and errors; reduction of the cost of the attracted resource; effective cost analysis of new banking products and services; conducting management accounting in accordance with international standards; - creation of a team of highly qualified professionals and constant work on improving the staff motivation system. The term "strategy" in the modern sense has five different meanings:

1) the plan of top management to achieve long-term results that correspond to the goals and objectives of the organization;

2) the principle of behavior, following a certain model of behavior;

3) position - the location of certain goods in specific markets (creating a unique and valuable position through a variety of actions);

4) perspective, that is, the main mode of action of the organization, its "business theory" aimed at the future of the enterprise;

5) reception - a special maneuver undertaken in order to outwit a competitor, involves exceptional pressure on a competitor, and not real adherence to the content of this information. The conceptual basis of the bank's activity, which defines the main goals and objectives, as well as the ways of their implementation based on the principles of development, is the bank's development strategy. It serves as a key for the bank's managers (management) to make major decisions on the development of prospective markets, their products, organization of the structure, calculation of risks and profitability of the bank at all its levels of operation. That is, it is the basis of the entire banking management system. The development strategy of the bank is a comprehensively developed detailed plan, which should in the future fulfill the set goals and its mission. In other words, a comprehensively developed step-by-step comprehensive plan for the implementation of the bank's work and development in the specified areas is the bank's development strategy aimed at implementing its mission and goals. The strategy is the accumulation of available funds and tools, as well as a plan for their application to solve the tasks set. The philosophical idea of banking of each bank is the daily painstaking work of highly qualified specialists. It is a high responsibility to work with clients' money. However, the bank, through its professional activities, helps to multiply the wealth of its customers and itself in the name of a better future. The objectives of the bank's development strategy are as follows: - to ensure maximum business profit; - to disperse the funds of the loan portfolio and income structure in order to reduce economic risks; - to improve the quality of the customer base; - to increase the efficiency of corporate governance by implementing high standards; - to multiply the customer base and expand the range of services offered for corporate as well as for private clients; - to strengthen the brand; - improve the quality of customer service; - expand the introduction of innovation and high technology products; - improve the efficiency of the operating

system; - develop alternative service and sales opportunities in a complex with an increase in the number of offices; - in accordance with the technology transfer plan, the strategic partner should effectively implement an increase in the number of various innovative banking products in the product line and the rapid development of information technology; - by applying a system of balanced indicators, manage the bank's ability to compete and carry out effective activities with partners; - establish and develop long-term partnership relations with the bank's service consumers, find mutually beneficial financial solutions for large, medium, and small businesses, non-residents of the bank and individuals; - consistently implement the created system of customer relations, which consists of identifying target groups of customers, finding and anticipating their needs, creating value chains: "target customer - offering him a banking product - banking services - value and benefit for the customer - profitability of the bank"; - applying a systematic approach to banking customers, to sell at least 4-5 products of the bank and accompany the development of clientele activities in the context of deep penetration into the needs of a particular client, business or industry; - to develop in detail and methodically implement programs for the development and training of personnel, organize and search for personnel and hire them, retain personnel and improve their activities, stimulate the motivation of trained personnel based on an understanding of the uniqueness and uniqueness of the human asset of this bank and the impact on increasing competitive ability.

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